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Jalaluddin Rumi the Poet: His Unshakable Popularity and Growing Acceptance across the World

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***Abstract:** Maulana Jalal-ud-Din Mohammad Rumi (1207-1273), a Persian mystic poet of the 13th century and a spiritual guide, took the world by storm with a treasure of his gifts of writings like poems, lyrics, rubaiyats and other writings on multiple themes. Poet Rumi is not totally comprehensible to the highly potential intellects and even to the spiritualists because of his airy nature far from the mundane world of reality. With the passage of time, his poems, composed in Persian language and translated in various tongues, captured the attention of the world-wide heedful readers and therefore, he was able to find a permanent place in readers' hearts. In fact, this study aims at projecting the real grounds of Rumi's astounding popularity across the world covering a span of 800 years. This study also highlights the major aspects of Rumi that have been fostering his growing acceptance as a poet and a Sufi. This article also discovers that, his short sayings having profundity appear like gems to the world readers, because these convey messages of eternal peace and harmony and of love and wisdom, required for the tormented souls in every society of every age.*

Keywords: Messages, Popularity, Readers, Sufism, Wisdom

Introduction

Maulana Jalaluddin Mohammad Rumi (1207-1273) is said to be the greatest Sufi poet the world has ever seen. Jalaluddin Rumi is deemed by both the East and the West as one of the greatest mystics as he was a descendent of the holy Prophet (Sm) from maternal side and of the First Caliph Hazrat Abu Bakar (Ra) from paternal side. On 30 September 1207, the poet, a royal descendant, was born in Balkh, now Afghanistan. 'He was born a strange child, a self-realised soul and a master of love.' His father called Bahauddin Valad was a theologian and a mystic preacher. On account of the wild Mongol aggression, their family left Balkh, accomplished hajj in Makkah, and at last decided to permanently live in the then Turkey. 'There Rumi grew up in an environment of practicing Sufism, a mystical path leading to the quest of Divine love and knowledge, having direct communion with Allah.' During his 30s, all on a sudden, he met Shams Tabriz, a wandering Sufi mystic who brought marked changes in his life. After coming in contact with this mysterious person possessing occult knowledge of Divinity, Rumi was inwardly transformed into a new one. His relationship with such a spiritual guide gradually grew profound, and they were supposed to lead a symbiotic life. But after four years, his dear guide Shams Tabriz disappeared; it is the opinion of some that he was allegedly murdered. As a result, Rumi sank within and plunged into an ocean of grief. Rumi experienced a shattered life; on the other hand he was as if born a new and engaged himself to writing.

Rumi died in Konya in southern part of Turkey on 17 December 1273. It is said that a crowd of local Jews and Christians carried his coffin through the city and he was buried beside his father. His beautiful shrine, now called Green Tomb, is known as Maulana Museum.

Jalaluddin Rumi was unquestionably a prolific author. His spontaneity in composing different types of poems and verses is unparalleled. Pretty often, we are blinded and sundered as well by

our differences, but Rumi preached that, first and foremost, we are all human beings; we are equally created. We do not always share the same principles, virtues and values. The following famous poem expresses his concept, as rare as deeply thoughtful:

Only Breath

Not Christian or Jew or Muslim, not Hindu
Buddhist, sufi, or zen. Not any religion
or cultural system. I am not from the East
or the West, not out of the ocean or up
from the ground, not natural or ethereal, not
composed of elements at all. I do not exist,
am not an entity in this world or in the next,
did not descend from Adam and Eve or any
origin story. My place is placeless, a trace
of the traceless. Neither body nor soul.
I belong to the beloved, have seen the two
worlds as one and that one call to and know,
first, last, outer, inner, only that
breath breathing human being.

In this short poem, Rumi highlights the practice of both religious and racial tolerance. Not only this, the prime need of peace and forbearance Rumi has focused on is a vital theme of his work and so he has been universally regarded as "his doctrine advocates tolerance, reasoning, goodness, charity and awareness through love, looking with the same eye on Muslims, Jews, Christians and others alike," according to the UMass Rumi Club website.

Brief Account of Rumi's Writings

Rumi, mainly wrote poems in Arabic and Persian; he also wrote some in Turkish and Greek. He wrote more than 3,000 ghazals, in Arabic concerning 'love and loss,' and more than 2,000 rubaiyat. Rumi composed his immortal work *Masnawi*, a great book on Sufism. It is deemed the most inspiring, influential and generally

termed as "the Persian Quran"—a series of a total of six books of poems having about 25,000 verses or 50,000 lines. About this work Narguess Farzad says: "His six-volume magnum opus of Spiritual Verses alone is five times the length of Milton's *Paradise Lost*, and then there are the 3,000-plus ecstatic hymns to love and the many quatrains that makes it near impossible to choose a favourite, "Books 1 and 2 " are principally concerned with the nafs, the lower carnal self, and its self-deception and evil tendencies." Book 3 and Book 4 deal with the themes of Reason and Knowledge. Books 5 and 6 are "joined by the universal ideal that man must deny his physical earthly existence to understand Allah's existence. These two themes are personified by Rumi in the Biblical and Quranic figure of the Prophet Moses." *Mathnawi* or *masnavi* is a kind of poem written in rhyming couplets, following a meter of eleven, or at times ten, syllables, but without limit in their length. Rumi's other works are *Diwan-e Shams-e Tabrizi* in honour of Shams, teacher of Rumi. Besides, there are approximately 35000 Persian couplets and 2000 Persian quatrains. There are prose works like *Fihi Ma Fihi* which is a document of 71 (seventy-one) lectures by Rumi on various occasions to his disciples. *Majāles-e Sab'a* contains 7 (seven) Persian sermons or lectures delivered to seven different assemblies. Rumi's *Maktubat*, a collection of letters in Persian, is written to the members of his family, disciples and men dealing with state affairs. A good number of experts have translated *Masnavi* and other poems in English. Of them, Redhouse, Wilson, Nicholson, Mojaddedi, Whinfield, Arberry, Helminski etc. are renowned. Rumi's poems are also translated into "many world's languages, including Russian, German, Urdu, Turkish, Arabic, Bengali, French, Italian, and Spanish, and are being presented in a growing number of formats, including concerts, workshops, readings, dance performances, and other artistic creations."

Rumi and His Enormous Popularity

Rumi has been teaching us as the most popular poet of the world for long 800 years. In recent years, millions of copies of his

ecstatic poems have been sold, making him the most popular poet not only in the Islamic world, but also in the US and Western Europe. By the end of the 20th century, his poems were greeted and attained a wide acclaim. So, his popularity is still unquestionable across the globe and there are a good number of reasons for such popularity: For long 800 years, the writings of poet Rumi have provided people of all ages and religions, origins and sects with inspiration and consolation. His teachings have acted miraculously for the development of human spirit. Rumi, the mystic poet, has opulently been quoted for centuries by different nations and cultures. Rumi's writings have been paved with transcendental qualities. "Beautiful, sonorous poetry has always been a balm for Rumi, who is amongst only a handful of poets throughout history who defy the passage of time and linguistic barriers, and speak to the soul of mankind," says Narguess Farzad (Rumi, *The Mathnawi of Jalaluddin Rumi*). Rumi introduces the Sufi practice of the Whirling Dervish dances. Each step of such Whirling dance unfolds the themes found in Rumi verses: Sufi practice. *Mathnawi* starts thus:

Book VI. Prologue

O spiritual one, I now offer it to thee,
This sixth part of the entire Masnavi.
Enlighten the world's six sides with its six parts,
That it may illuminate him who is not illuminated!
Love has naught to do with five senses or six sides,
Its only aim is to be attracted to the Beloved!
(Rumi, *The Mathnawi*)

A number of Rumi poems appear to be about love and romance and it is at the surface level. But, when the readers of Rumi learn that, those who love with the touch of their eyes, do not actually see love. Instead, those who, in fact, love with their heart and soul, do not suffer from separation. And separation to them 'does not

mean mere distance from a lover or loved one, but from a kind of inner feeling, or inexplicable experience.’

Rumi in his sublime body of poetry encapsulates the causes of separation from the omnipotent Creator and deals with this theme very adroitly. The Rumi readers by learning these find consolation in their heart and so Rumi is popular to them.

“Rumi was an experimental innovator among the Persian poets and he was a Sufi master,” says Jawid Mojaddedi, “This combination of mystical richness and bold adaptations of poetic forms is the key to his popularity today.” Of Rumi’s four main innovations, the first is his direct address to readers in the second person, says Mojaddedi. “I think contemporary readers respond well to this directness.” Secondly, it is his urge to teach: “Readers of ‘inspirational’ literature are drawn to Rumi’s poetry.” Third, “his use of everyday imagery.” And fourth, “his optimism of the attainment of union within his lyrical love ghazals in which Rumi celebrates union.”

One of the strong reasons of Rumi’s popularity is that he created the positive inspiration. He never succumbs to dejection and despair though there were the agonies of soul sundered from a beloved or a lover or a root source of life. This concept of Rumi still energizes psychologically the perturbed human minds. All these make him extremely popular not only in the Persian speaking world but also in the domains torn asunder by strife, factions, sects and differences in opinions.

From the very beginning of his initiation to the path of Sufism, and after coming in contact with Shams Tabriz, ‘Rumi’s love for, and his bereavement at the death of, Shams found their expression in an outpouring of lyric poems, *Divan-e Shams-e Tabrizi* (Rumi, *Dewan-e-Shams Tarbiz*). He himself went out searching for Shams and journeyed again to Damascus. There, he realised:

Why should I seek? I am the same as

He. His essence speaks through me.
I have been looking for myself!

The people are stimulated and heartened by this enlightening concept. Also, Rumi dealt with this mystical approach of Islam "a school of practice that emphasizes the inward search for God and shuns materialism," according to The New York Times, "is drawn to one that alludes to both the Biblical and Quranic story of the first creation of man, which Farzad has translated appears thus."

The dew of Love
turned a lump of clay
into Adam
and the whole world
was stirred with fervour and joy
A hundred cupid lances pierced the veins of Spirit,
one drop fell to earth
and they named it Heart!

Rumi's messages concerning love, self-empowerment, and spiritual development, enlightenment of soul, self-realization, ultimate ascension, and above all imponderable tolerance for various religious concepts are truly timeless. The people are inspired by these messages to a great extent. The following Rumi poem is a glaring example:

From the dust of the earth to a human being,
there are a thousand steps.
I have been with you through these steps,
I have held your hand and walked by your side.
And I will be with you
as you move beyond this human form
and soar to the highest heavens.

Besides, there are a number of reasons for which Rumi's popularity is undeniable. His poems spoke to all, irrespective of caste, creed and religion, for the correction of their souls.

When someone beats a rug,
the blows are not against the rug,
but against the dust in it.

Here, for conveying his message to the heedful readers, Rumi uses familiar objects. In addition to all these, there are countless animals and objects such as ‘elephant, an artist, pearls, shepherds, dragons, housewives and chickpeas.’ Thus his poems have generally grown familiar to everyone. Not only this, his poems teach us not to think of ourselves as worthless:

You are more precious than both heaven and earth:
You know not your own worth
Sell not yourself at a little price,
Being so precious in God’s eyes.

Rumi’s message was universal. He discovered the Divine within his heart though he was quite aware of mosques, temples, churches and other prayer-houses. During his time, Rumi, a true practicing Muslim, was a celebrated Islamic Scholar, a jurist and a theologian. He said, ‘As long as I live, I am the slave of the Quran I am the dust of the path of Muhammad.’

Rumi’s Growing Acceptance to the Generations

Rumi’s religious outlook is universal. He was a philosopher and his philosophical concepts are transcendental ‘like a string through the beads of his poems and stories.’ Human life has ups and downs. In such ebb and flow of life, the essential verses of Rumi prove to be a source of continuous inspiration. His poems can spark expectations and dreams and also kindle essential purpose in your journey along the tortuous paths to the goals. When Rumi says:

“Yesterday I was clever, and I wanted to change the world
Today I am wise, and I want to change myself.”

In fact, where is our place, where are we located? Where will we be sought? It is not a matter at all to feel ourselves small and insignificant in this turbulent world, torn asunder by factions, contradictory opinions, skirmishes and fearful battles. Here, we explore some relevant Rumi poems as inspiring messages that increases Rumi's acceptance:

On the Turn

I am so small I can barely be seen.
How can this great love be inside me?
Look at your eyes. They are small,
But they see enormous things.

Rumi's acceptance to the generations always accelerates. It is not difficult to follow a common beaten track, by following of which people have already found successes. But, fortune never smiles upon a number of men who follow such path. They are really lost souls. Possibly that beaten track is not for them. Here Rumi awakens them and ask them to forget mere tales:

Unfold Your Own Myth

But don't be satisfied with stories,
How things have gone with others.
Unfold your own myth,

Jalaluddin Rumi wrote a large number of inspirational poems that can transform human life into a new. One should dispel laziness, apathetic attitudes to life. So, attempts should be made to use our abilities. The following poem can teach us how to avoid fear which is nothing but a reality. Humans are always concerned with fear from people and various kinds of things.

The Uses of Fear

We look to ease our pain, and this keeps civilization
Moving along. Fear is the architect here.

Fear keeps us working near the ark.

Such poems are essentially effective for building up human careers. We should look at things in different ways and more resonate with them. The bond of Love is very powerful and Rumi teaches how to connect love with body, mind and soul.

The modern people are acquainted with the universality of Rumi. According to Professor Majid M. Naini, "Rumi's life and transformation provide the true testimony and proof that people of all religions and backgrounds can live together in peace and harmony. Rumi's visions, words, and life teach us how to gain inner peace and happiness. So we can finally stop the continual stream of hostility and hatred and achieve true global peace and harmony." The Mevlevi order delivers an invitation to people from various walks of life:

Come, come, whoever you are,
Wanderer, idolater, worshiper of fire,
Come even though you have broken your vows a thousand
times,
Come, and come yet again.
Ours is not a caravan of despair (*Hanut*).

In the world the brave can generally win. And they experience a remarkable life. The first step for such people is always very tough. But bold decision can transform thoughts going forward. So, people can find inspiration in the following poem. Thus Rumi's growing acceptance to people has started increasing.
All Rivers at Once

What is the body? Endurance.
What is love? Gratitude.
What is hidden in our chests? Laughter.
What else? Compassion.

He also learnt that though people's beliefs are different, they are basically identical. At last he understood that only Sufi doctrine can bring about a change in the inner state of a man, and this concept grew strong to him when he came into a deep contact with the mysterious Sufi-personality Shams-ud- Din of Tabriz, having a highly developed soul. The union with Shams inflamed the sun of love into Rumi's soul. Rumi says of Shams:

The face of Shamsi Din, Tabriz's glory, is the sun
In whose track the cloud-like hearts are moving.
O Shamsi Tabriz, beauty and glory of the horizons,
What king but is a beggar of thee with heart and soul?
(Davis 32)

Rumi said about his epic *Masnawi* that it is 'the root of the root of the Root of all religions.' This invaluable document of mysticism is the interpretation of the progressive Sufi-path. Jalaluddin exclaimed that great love is silent and incomparable.

I am silent. Speak Thou, O soul of soul of soul,
From desire of whose Face every atom grew articulate.

Regarding 'Noor' Moulana Rumi, in his mystic verses, has said that we are the shadows of Allah. We have come from 'Noor -i - Muhammadi', we are the invaluable pearl cast inside the oysters. A great Sufi Sheikh Fariduddin Attar (1136-1230) has beautifully expressed his concept of Noor:

I am a pure light that has entered in a handful of dust
But how will the blind find its brightness.
I am light of the light, light of the light am I, I am only light
and light
I am not the lamp, neither am I the wick, nor am I burning
oil.

Shams-od-Din Hafiz's poem also embodies the same implication:

Open my grave after my death and look
How by reason of the fire within me smoke rises from my
shroud.

Sayings of Rumi as a Proverbial Poet

Rumi is a proverbial poet. His simple and forcible mode of expressing thoughts and ideas gave birth to countless proverbial expressions. His Sayings on love, wisdom, peace, harmony, inspiration, motivation, life etc. are inconceivably effective in infusing strength and energy in human life. As a result, deep-seated despair and soul-injuring dejection can be dispelled.

Aishwarya Bhargav says, “Rumi, a 13th Century Philosopher authored over five hundred quotes on love, life, friendship, beauty and healing. In addition to being a philosopher, Rumi was an Islamic Scholar and a theologian. In his lifetime Rumi composed several Persian poems and prose compositions. His work gained prominence in the 20th Century, when scholars delved into his work and began to translate it in a bid to enrich the world.”

The Rumi’s Quotes possess the ability by offering helpless souls losing paths to taste reality if they really desire to be transformed. The majority of the Rumi’s Quotes can be taken as proverbs. Some Sayings of such a proverbial poet are cited below:

1. You can’t mend something that is not broken! To be healed, you need to fall ill.
2. Don’t let anything get to your head. Be it happiness, pride or sadness.
3. As the day ends, a new one begins in another part of the world. What goes around will come back to you.
4. Healing begins with you. Irrespective of what the world says, you make your own little world by changing yourself.
5. When setting out on a journey, do not seek advice from those who have never left home.

6. If you want something, release the wish, and let it light on its desire, completely free of the personal.
7. The desire to know your own soul will end all other desires.
8. Just as the water reflects the stars and the moon, the body reflects the mind and soul.
9. Peaceful is the one who is not concerned with having more or less.
10. Once you conquer your selfish self, all your darkness will change to light.
11. Be like a tree and let the dead leaves drop.
12. When I think I am, I find myself worthless. When I think I am not, I find my value.
13. Behind every atom of this world hides an infinite universe.
14. When you feel a peaceful joy, that's when you are near (the) truth.
15. Being a candle is not easy; in order to give light one must first burn.
16. Don't grieve. Anything you lose comes round in another form.
17. Your radiance shines in every atom of creation yet our petty desires keep it hidden.
18. There is a voice that doesn't use words. Listen.
19. The quieter you become the more you are able to hear.
20. Do not feel lonely; the entire universe is inside you.
21. Be certain that in the religion of Love there are no believers and unbelievers. LOVE embraces all.
22. Let silence take you to the core of life.
23. Seek the wisdom that will untie your knot. Seek the path that demands your whole being.
24. Maybe you are searching among the branches for what only appears in the roots.
25. Just as the water reflects the stars and the moon, the body reflects the mind and soul.
26. Be a lamp, a lifeboat, a ladder. Help someone's soul heal. Walk out of your house like a shepherd.
27. Love is the bridge between you and everything.

The above Rumi quotes will bring inner peace and contentment, wisdom, love, life, inner peace and patience that can transform life.

Findings and Opinions

- In ‘The New Yorker’ Rozina Ali wrote: Rumi “is typically referred to as a mystic, a saint, a Sufi and an enlightened man. Curiously, however, although he was a lifelong scholar of the Qur’an and Islam, he is less frequently described as a Muslim. The erasure of Islam from Rumi’s poetry started long ago. This was a time when Muslims were singled out for legal discrimination—a law from 1790 curtailed the number of Muslims who could come into the United States, and a century later the U.S. Supreme Court described the ‘intense hostility of the people of Moslem faith to all other sects, and particularly to Christians’” (Ali).
- Sometimes, a number of intellects think of Rumi’s ‘humanistic thoughts’ as ‘religious pluralism’ which was shaped by English Philosopher John Hick who says, “it was taught by such thinkers as Rumi and Al-Arabi in the 13th century....” (Hick). Also, it is learnt that the central idea of the small poem ‘Only Breath’, mentioned earlier is that Rumi is ‘a breathing human being’ and he ‘belongs to the beloved.’ It is the concept of human creation.
- In 1898, Sir James Redhouse wrote in his exhaustive introduction to his translation of the *Masnavi*, “The *Masnavi* addresses those who leave the world, try to know and be with God, efface their selves and devote themselves to spiritual contemplation...In the twentieth century, a succession of prominent translators—among them R. Nicholson, A. J. Arberry, and Annemarie Schimmel—strengthened Rumi’s presence in the English-language canon. But it’s [Coleman] Barks who vastly expanded Rumi’s readership” (Redhouse). Thus ‘the erasure of Islam from Rumi’s poetry’ started long ago stopped forever and Rumi has already gained ground immeasurably in the US and the West as well.

- Whirling Dervish Dance is deemed a form of meditation or a form of dhikr or remembrance of Allah, presented by the dervishes in Mevlevi order or *tariqa*, expounded by Rumi who, it is said that, one day Rumi was passing through a town. Suddenly he heard the mild hammer-blows of a goldsmith and the blows were rhythmic. In sounds of such unceasing beating, Rumi perceived *dhikr* 'La Ilaha Illallah'. He grew overjoyed and stretching out his arms, started spinning in a circle in an ecstasy. There are many roads leading to Allah. One such road is this Whirling dervish dance.

Recommendations

- We are living in an era full of chaos and turmoil. We are passing through an ordeal. Thus world peace is in an appalling state. People in general are bored. So, in such a terrible situation, we should isolate scintillating Rumi messages from the immortal pages of his verses and devote our mind to imbibe their essence and as per necessity to combat the challenges we are facing.
- There are a good number of positive advices, enshrined in the poems of Rumi, in the form of suggestions that we should cultivate in our life and character to get out of the mortal frowning of the present age.
- We must be aware of a large number of quotable poetic lines, expressed metaphorically, antithetically and also with indirect expressions deemed to be the projection of his rare method and style, are highly useful and helpful in establishing peace and harmony in society.
- The people who are enthusiastically interested in exercising practices of Sufism and mysticism can draw ample benefit from Rumi's relevant messages by cultivating Divine love and wisdom.

- We can seek profuse hints and directions from the poems and verses of Jalal-ud-din Rumi and can cultivate them for the development of our soul, mind and spirit.
- A sincere reading of Rumi can help us dispel harmful emotive responses and the narrowness of our attitudes to world community, irrespective of caste, creed, religion and nation.
- In this post-modern era, Rumi Sayings sound like proverbs. So, if the relevant proverbial messages of the proverbial poet Rumi can properly be cultivated, then we can succeed in our earthly life as well as in the life hereafter.

Conclusion

Rumi has a great number of followers in the USA as well as in other countries. “Rumi's importance is considered ‘to transcend national and ethnic borders.’ If anyone needs an excellent picture of love and life, these Rumi sayings will expand his mind in various ways by providing an insight from ‘a great wordsmith’ of the 13th century. As Edward G. Browne noted, “the three most prominent mystical Persian poets Rumi, Sanai and Attar were all Sunni Muslims and their poetry abounds with praise for the first two caliphs Abu Bakr and Umar ibn al-Khattāb.” According to the Quran, Muhammad is a mercy sent by God (*The Quranic Arabic Corpus*). With regard to this, Rumi states:

"The Light of Muhammad has become a thousand branches (of knowledge), a thousand, so that both this world and the next have been seized from end to end. If Muhammad rips the veil open from a single such branch, thousands of monks and priests will tear the string of false belief from around their waists." Thus Rumi states:

I am the servant of the Qur'an as long as I have life.
I am the dust on the path of Muhammad, the Chosen one.
If anyone quotes anything except this from my sayings,
I am quit of him and outraged by these words (*Gamard*).

Brad Gooch, who wrote a biography of Rumi, describes him as “a poet of joy and of love” (Gooch). To simply epitomize, Rumi’s concepts are life-based, mind-concerned and soul-oriented. Thus Rumi’s popularity and acceptance to the interested souls and readers across the world are ascertained.

Acknowledgements

Most of the small poems used in the article are taken from the following sources. So, the author heartily acknowledges to:

- (1) “What Rumi, The World’s Most Popular Poet, Wants to Teach Us, 800 Years Later”, written by Michelle Konstantirorsry, Housestuffwox, 4235, Redwood
- (2) “8 Exquisitely Beautiful Rumi Poems to Inspire Your Life,” Mindvalley, Harjumaa Tallinn Linn Leava tn. 1 10411
- (3) Most of the Rumi Quotes and Sayings are taken from “Top Rumi Quotes to celebrate Love, Life, Nature, Sufism & the Universe” Wings, Office: Devonshire House, 60 Goswell Road, UK, EC1M 7AD (Source: From Internet)

Works Cited

- Ali, Rozina. “Rumi and Whirling Dervishes—Facts and Details”. *The New Yorker*. January, 2017,
- Bhargav, Aishwarya. 10 Rumi Quotes on Healing: Inspiring Quotes that Will Unburden Your Soul. *Inspire Me: A Mental Health & Psychology Portal*. November, 2017
- Davis, Hadland. *The Persian Mystics Jalalu’d_din Rumi*. Published by SH. Muhammad Ashraf, Kashmiri Bazar, Lahore. 1907.
- Gamard, Ibrahim. “Rumi and Self Discovery. *Dar al Masnavi*”. April, 1999, www.dar-almasnavi.org/self-discovery.html.
- Gooch, Brad. *Rumi's Secret: The Life of the Sufi Poet of Love*. Harper, New York. 2017.

- Hanut, Eryk, and Michele, Wetherbee. "Rumi: The Card and Book Pack: Meditation, Inspiration, and Self-discovery." January Editions, 2000.
- Hick, John. "Religious Pluralism and Islam." John Hick, 2005. www.johnhick.org.uk/article11.pdf.
- Juma, Nobert, Lifestyle Writer and Editor, "EverydayPower.com," 2013-2022, <https://everydaypower.com/author/norbertjuma/>
- Konstantinovskiy, Michelle. "What Rumi, the World's Most Popular Poet, Wants to Teach Us, 800 Years Later", HowStuffWorks, 4235 Redwood Ave., Marina Del Rey, CA 90066. October, 2020.
- Mojaddedi, Jawid. "Beyond Dogma: Rumi's Teachings on Friendship with God and Early Sufi Theories". <https://www.investintech.com › blog › archives › 1006>.
- Naini, Mazid. *The Mysteries of the Universe and Rumi's Discoveries on the Majestic Path of Love*, translations from Rumi's original Persian texts, Amazon, Paperback. 2002.
- Peer, Marisa. "Rapid Transformational Therapy Quest", *Mindvalley*, <https://blog.mindvalley.com>, London, UK. November, 2017.
- Rumi, Maulana Jalal al-Din, *Rumi and Islam: Selections from His Stories, Poems, and Discourses-- Annotated & Explained*. Translated by Ibrahim Gamard, Skylight Paths Publishing, 2000, p.163.
- Rumi, Jalaluddin. *The Mathnawi of Jalaluddin Rumi – Book 6: Spiritual Couplets of Mystical Meaning*. Edited by Michael Bielas, translated by Reynold Alleyne Nicholson, 2020.
- Rumi, *Shour-e Shams: A Rumi Anthology of Diwan-e Kabir Shams-i Tabrizi*. Abbas Behnejad (ed). Araye, 2013.
- Rumi, Maulana J. A. *Communion with God*. The Masnavi: Book 5, Great Sages Publishing, 2017.
- Redhouse, James William. *The Mesnevi and the Acts of the Adept*. *Library of Alexandria*, 2009.
- Shiva, Shahram. "Rumi's Untold Story: From 30-Year Research", Rumi Network. rumi.net. art/performance/music scene, 2018.

UMass Rumi Club website. (Campus Certerway, Amherst,
MA01003, USA, email: rumi@resgs.umass.edu
*“Verse (21:107) – English Translation.” The Quranic Arabic
Corpus*